

after sowing (DAS) and 25% N at 40 DAS.

Data on average depth of seed placement, seed distribution efficiency (SDE), plant population/ m-row length,

energy use efficiency (EUE), and comparative performance index (CPI = product of energy, SDE, and grain yield factors) are in Table 2. The two-row implement factory seed-cum-fertilizer

drill had the highest CPI (3.33), SDE (81%), and number of plants/m-row (28). The three-row drill appeared to have had higher friction in the metering device. □

Environmental analysis

Effect of season on rice response, production efficiency, and recovery of applied N

M. A. Salam, Cropping Systems Research Centre, Karamana 695002, Trivandrum; and S. Subramanian, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Coimbatore 641003, India

We studied the response, production efficiency, and recovery of applied N in rice, with and without soil-applied granular insecticides during the southwest monsoon (Jun-Sep 1982), northeast monsoon (Sep-Dec 1982), summer (Jan-Apr 1983), and southwest monsoon (Jan-Sep 1983).

Soil was clay loam, pH 8.2, with 1% organic matter, 196-9.5-200 ppm available NPK, 598 ppm total soil N, and 0.4 ppm DTPH extractable Zn. The experiments were factorial combinations

of 4 levels of N (0, 60, 90, and 120 kg/ha) and 3 levels of insecticides (no insecticide, carbofuran 3% granular at 0.75 kg ai/ha, and phorate 10% granules at 1.0 kg ai/ha) in a randomized block design with 6 replications.

Rice response to N (kg grain produced: kg of N applied) and N recovery were highest when N was applied with carbofuran or phorate (see table).

Across the seasons, response and N recovery were higher in summer; production efficiency was higher in the northeast monsoon season. □

Response, production efficiency, and recovery of N applied with and without insecticide, by season.^a Coimbatore, India, 1982-83.

	SWM 1982	NEM 1982	SUM 1983	SWM 1983
<i>Response (kg grain:kg N)</i>				
N alone	12	12	16	21
N + carbofuran at 0.75 kg ai/ha	19	20	25	22
N + phorate at 1.0 kg ai/ha	20	21	26	25
<i>Production efficiency (kg grain:kg N)</i>				
N alone	39	70	45	56
N + carbofuran at 0.75 kg ai/ha	34	12	41	56
N + phorate at 1.0 kg ai/ha	38	23	44	66
<i>N recovery (%)</i>				
N alone	28	17	38	34
N + carbofuran at 0.75 kg ai/ha	55	29	62	39
N + phorate at 1.0 kg ai/ha	53	29	58	34

^aSWM = southwest monsoon, NEM = northeast monsoon, SUM = summer.

Farming systems

Growth and yield of wet season rice with tilapia fish

S. K. Datta and S. H. Ghosh, Field Crop Research Station, Bardhaman; and C. N. Bairagya, Radha Fish Farm, Bardhaman, West Bengal, India

We studied growth and yield of rice and fish in the Cropping Systems Research site at Memari in 1987 (Jun-Dec) wet season. The experiment consisted of a plot of rice without fish and one of rice with tilapia (*Oreochromis mossambicus*).

Soil was clay loam with pH 6.5 - 7.0.

Plots were thoroughly plowed and 9 t farmyard manure/ha incorporated. Plots were 20 × 38 m with a shallow 75- × 50-cm perimeter canal and a trapezoidal protective dike bounding the canal. To encourage better fish movement, 2 central drains, each 50 cm wide and 30 cm deep, were dug lengthwise across the plot of rice with fish.

Pankaj, a recommended photoperiod-sensitive lowland rice variety, was transplanted, 2 seedlings at 15- × 20-cm spacing/hill, in early Aug, with 100 kg N/ha applied 1/2 at land preparation and 1/2 in equal splits 1 mo after transplanting and 1 wk before flowering; 18 kg P and 33 kg K/ha were added at land preparation. Pump water was used

Growth and yield of rice + fish at Bardhaman, West Bengal, 1987 wet season.

Characteristic	Rice without fish	Rice + fish
<i>Rice</i>		
Plant height (cm)	133.2	120.8
Effective tillers/plant	12.0	15.2
Panicle length (cm)	26.4	26.8
Grains/panicle	158.2	178.4
Grain yield (t/ha)	4.1	4.9
Straw yield (t/ha)	5.2	6.0
<i>Fish</i>		
Recovery (%)	—	81.3
Increase in length (cm)	—	8.2
Increase in weight (g)	—	96.4
Fish yield (t/ha)	—	0.7

to irrigate as needed. Water depth, 3-5 cm at the outset, was gradually increased to 10-12 cm.

Tilapia fingerlings were stocked at 2 fish/m² 35 d after transplanting. They were fed an inexpensive 1:1 mixture of rice bran and mustard cake at 5% total body weight each morning. When fertilizer was topdressed, the water level was gradually lowered so that fish could take refuge in the drains.

Fish were harvested with rice in mid-Dec. A few hours before harvest, plots

were slowly drained, allowing the fish to move to the drains where they could be collected by dragnet and hand. Rice was cut with hand sickles about 15-20 cm from the ground and bound into small bundles. The bundles were placed in rows over the stubble so that they did not touch the muddy ground.

Ten randomly selected plants from each plot were uprooted at harvest for

data collection. Growth and yield data for 10 randomly selected fish and total yields were recorded (see table).

With rice + fish, growth and yield characters of rice increased appreciably while plant height decreased. Fish weight and length increased considerably during the 4 mo cropping duration. □

Pulse crop performance in a rice-based cropping sequence

K. Sudhakara Babu, K. Ramaseshaiah, and Y. P. Prabhakara Rao, Regional Agricultural Research Station, Lam Farm, Guntur 522034, Andhra Pradesh, India

Farmers of coastal Andhra Pradesh, India, grow black gram *Vigna mungo* (L) Hepper as a relay crop with rainy season rice in about 0.25 million ha. Black gram seed is broadcast into the standing rice crop 24 d before rice harvest mid-Nov to mid-Dec. The black gram grows entirely on residual moisture and fertility, with no intercultivation or weeding. Average yield is about 0.8 t/ha. But recently black gram has suffered from wilt, root

Grain yield and gross return^a from different pulse crops. Andhra Pradesh, India, 1980-83.

Crop	Grain yield (t/ha)				Gross return (\$/ha)			
	1980-81	1981-82	1982-83	Mean	1980-81	1981-82	1982-83	Mean
Black gram	1.10	0.91	1.08	1.03	232	188	331	250
Mungbean	0.65	0.37	0.91	0.64	179	85	227	164
Chickpea	^b	0.07	0.05	0.06	^b	17	13	15
Cowpea	0.71	0.51	0.32	0.51	109	98	74	94
Pigeonpea	0.34	0.19	0.11	0.21	78	44	38	53
Soybean	0.07	^b	0.13	0.10	15	^b	35	25

^aUS\$1 = Rs 13.04. ^bFailed.

rot, and powdery mildew diseases. We evaluated five alternate pulse crops after rainy season rice in 1980-81 to 1982-83. The experimental site was a black alluvium under Krishna delta. Rice variety BPT3291 was transplanted the first week of Aug with 80-20-37 kg NPK/ha. Pulse crops were broadcast in

the standing rice crop 3 d before rice harvest.

Soybean, pigeonpea, and chickpea, with higher yield potential than black gram, did not do well (see table). Mungbean and cowpea yields were satisfactory, but less than that of black gram. □

ANNOUNCEMENTS

New IRRI publications

Rice seed health

Rice ratooning

Helpful insects, spiders, and pathogens—friends of the rice farmer (in Cebuano)

New book on rice diseases

Advances in rice pathology, 484 pp, edited by S. Kannaiyan, was published

Sep 1987 by Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, India. Its 24 chapters were written by 31 plant pathologists with broad experience in India, Bangladesh, the United States, and IRRI.

Chapters cover a broad spectrum of recent developments in rice disease management, including mechanisms of resistance, pathogenic races, epidemiology, disease forecasting, ecology of pathogens, insect vectors,

nematodes, microorganisms in postharvest handling, as well as breeding for resistance and disease control.

To order, contact S. Kannaiyan, Biotechnology Unit, Department of Agricultural Microbiology, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Coimbatore 641003, Tamil Nadu, India.

For instructions on preparation of brief reports of rice research to submit for publication in IRRN, see the inside front cover of this issue.